

EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF THE ACTIVITIES OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

A.A. Makhmudov

Independent researcher of the Law Enforcement Academy
of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation:

The article analyzes reforms of the prosecutor's office of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the era of New Uzbekistan. It outlines legislative and institutional changes that expanded prosecutorial functions, strengthened transparency and accountability, and enhanced protection of rights, demonstrating the transformation into a modern institution serving legality and society.

Keywords:

Prosecutorial service, prosecutorial reform; rule of law; human rights protection; anti-corruption measures; economic crimes; legal supervision; modernization.

From the very first days of our country's independence, consistent measures were undertaken to determine the legal status of law enforcement bodies, including the prosecutor's office, alongside the establishment of state power and administrative institutions, and to create the legislative foundations for their functioning. In particular, in recent years, large-scale reforms have been carried out in the field of the prosecutor's office aimed at ensuring transparency and fairness, adopting people-oriented decisions serving the interests of citizens and society, and shaping a system with its own theoretical and practical school, as well as a devoted and professional staff corps.

In this regard, the reforms implemented in the prosecutor's office of Uzbekistan from independence to the present day can conventionally be divided into three stages: 1) the period of establishing the legal foundations of the prosecutor's office in independent Uzbekistan (1991–2000); 2) the period of strengthening the role and position of the prosecutor's office within the system of state authorities (2001–2015); 3) the period of improving the activities of the prosecutor's office in the New Uzbekistan (from 2016 onwards).

During the first stage (1991–2000), namely the period of establishing the legal foundations of the prosecutor's office in independent Uzbekistan, the prosecutor's office was formed as a fully independent law enforcement institution. The Declaration of Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law “On the Foundations of State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan,” adopted on 31 August 1991, played a significant role in ensuring the genuine independence of the prosecutor's office. On the basis of Decree of the President No. DP-313 of 8 January 1992 “On the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan,” the Prosecution Office of the Uzbek SSR was transformed into the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In effect, on 8 January 1992, the prosecutor's office of independent Uzbekistan was established.

At that stage, the legal status of the prosecutor's office in independent Uzbekistan was defined, marking an important institutional step aimed at ensuring supreme supervision over the observance of laws, protecting the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens, and safeguarding the sovereignty of the country.

A historic milestone in determining the legal status of the prosecutor's office was the eleventh session of the twelfth convocation of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, held on 8 December 1992. Specifically, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted at this session established, in Chapter XXIV (Articles 118–121), key constitutional provisions regarding the position of the Prosecutor General, as well as the powers and status of the prosecutor's office,

thereby granting constitutional status to this institution. The adoption of this Law played a crucial role in defining the legal status of the prosecutor's office. The Law set forth the fundamental tasks, guiding principles, and directions of prosecutorial activity, as well as other matters related to the organization of work within the prosecutor's office.

The years 2001–2015 encompass the second stage of reforms implemented within the system of the prosecutor's office, which is significant as this period was marked by the improvement of the role and functions of the prosecutor's office within the system of state authorities. Above all, during these years, substantial efforts were made to reform prosecutorial activities, transforming the prosecutor's office into an institution that ensures the strict enforcement of laws, the consistent development of democratic reforms in the country, and the reliable protection of human rights and freedoms.

In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Prosecutor's Office,” adopted on 29 August 2001 in its new edition, introduced a number of democratic innovations and differed significantly from the previous law: 1) Citizens were excluded from the objects of prosecutorial supervision, while the functions of the prosecutor's office in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens were expanded; 2) For the first time, the prevention of offenses was established as one of the principal tasks of the prosecutor's office; 3) The legal status of prosecutorial supervision acts was reinforced, and the “order” (amrnoma) was excluded from the list of prosecutorial supervision documents; 4) Provisions were introduced regarding the coordination of activities of agencies engaged in combating crime; 5) A rule was established whereby orders and other acts of the Prosecutor General (except for those of an individual nature) may be annulled by a decision of the Constitutional Court if they contradict the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan; 6) The prosecutor’s authority to suspend court decisions

was abolished; 7) The powers of district and city prosecutors to extend the periods of investigation and detention of suspects were revoked [1], [2].

Furthermore, pursuant to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 11 March 2004, the Department for Supervising Compliance with the Law in the Enforcement of Court Judgments and in the Process of Detention of Persons in Custody, along with its territorial subdivisions, was established within the Office of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This served to ensure the realization of human rights through the proper enforcement of court judgments and to prevent unlawful restrictions of the legitimate rights and interests of persons held in correctional facilities.

It is well known that combating tax and currency-related offenses holds significant importance in the activities of the prosecutor's office. Therefore, in order to enhance the effectiveness of the fight against economic and tax-related crimes and to protect the economic interests of the state, legal entities, and individuals, by virtue of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of 6 July 2001 “On Measures to Strengthen the Fight Against Crimes in the Sphere of Economy and Taxation,” the Main Directorate for Combating Violations of Tax Legislation under the State Tax Committee was reorganized into the Department for Combating Tax and Currency-Related Crimes and Legalization of Proceeds of Crime under the Prosecutor General’s Office, along with its regional divisions [3]. Subsequently, pursuant to the Decree of the President of the Republic of the Uzbekistan No. DP-331 of 21 April 2006, this unit was transformed into the Department for Combating Tax and Currency-Related Crimes and Legalization of Criminal Proceeds under the Prosecutor General’s Office [4].

In general, the second stage of reforms of the prosecutor's office contributed to the further enhancement of its role and position in ensuring legality in society and consolidated its legal status in this regard.

The third stage in the development of the prosecutor's office — the period of improving its activities in the New Uzbekistan (*from 2016 onwards*) — may rightfully be described as the period when the prosecutor's office began to transform into a truly people-oriented prosecution service. As a result of the prudent policies of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, the prosecution system — one of the crucial “pillars” for implementing state mechanisms — was, figuratively speaking, revived after having been caught in a whirlpool of problems and brought to the brink of collapse.

This third stage marked the beginning of the transformation of the prosecutor's office. It has a special turning point in the history of this institution, as transparency and openness, along with the complete digitalization of prosecutorial activities, became key priorities. The principal requirement set by the President—understanding people, living with their joys and concerns, perceiving and assessing circumstances through the eyes of ordinary citizens, and never becoming detached from society—was established as a fundamental criterion for prosecutors as well [5].

During 2016–2024, nearly 30 normative legal acts concerning the activities of the prosecutor’s office were adopted, serving to fundamentally reform the system. In particular, within this period, the following legal acts aimed at further improving the activities of the prosecutor’s office and enhancing its role in society were adopted: the Law “On Combating Corruption” (2017); the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP–5019 of April 18, 2017 “On strengthening the role of the prosecutor's office in the implementation of socio-economic reforms, modernization of the country, ensuring reliable protection of human rights and freedoms”; the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP–5729 of May 29, 2019 “On measures to further improve the anti-corruption system in the Republic of Uzbekistan”; the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP–60 of January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of the New

Uzbekistan for 2022—2026” and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP–71 of April 21, 2025 “On measures to effectively organize the implementation of priority tasks identified for further improvement of the anti-corruption system,” along with other legal acts related to the sphere.

As Prosecutor General N. Yuldoshev noted, in recent years the entire profile of the prosecutor’s office has undergone a profound transformation [6]. One of the key reforms implemented during this stage in New Uzbekistan was the determination of the priority tasks of the prosecutor’s office under the initiative of President Sh. Mirziyoyev. In particular, special attention was paid to further strengthening the role of the prosecutor’s office in preventing embezzlement of budgetary funds and their misuse. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP–5446 of May 23, 2018 “On measures to radically increase the efficiency of using budget funds and improve mechanisms for combating economic crimes” acquired historical importance. According to this Decree, the Department on Combating Tax, Currency Crimes, and Legalization of Criminal Proceeds under the Prosecutor General’s Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan was reorganized into the Department for Combating Economic Crimes under the Prosecutor General’s Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This reform was of historic significance for ensuring economic security and more effective use of the state’s financial resources [7].

In recent years, specialized divisions have been established within the system to ensure the rule of law in such areas as the protection of cultural heritage and sports, entrepreneurship and investment, prevention of embezzlement in construction and land resources, as well as the protection of women’s rights and their defense against harassment and violence [8]. Furthermore, in 2023–2024, supervisory divisions were created to oversee compliance with legislation in the fields of ecology and environmental protection, combating the shadow economy, poverty reduction, and social protection of the population.

Overall, during this period, special attention was paid to establishing control over the implementation of laws in the country. The so-called “general supervision” function of the prosecutor’s office, as it became known among the people, underwent significant reform. As a result, the prosecutor’s office was transformed into a body that truly serves the people and reliably protects human rights and interests.

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